

CRTC - Radio Digital Monitoring System Project Digital Transformation & Metadata Normalization LATICCE FINAL REPORT

**Michèle Rioux Ph D., Jean-Robert Bisaillon PH D. Student and
Guy-Philippe Wells, PH D. Student**

LATICCE (CEIM-UQAM) - ceimlaticce@gmail.com

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LATICCE

LATICCE is a division of CEIM (Globalization and Integration Study Center) based at Quebec University in Montreal. This multi-faculty lab has devoted the last two years measuring the level of content discoverability on global musical, film and eBook platforms.

Michèle Rioux is professor of political economy at the Department of political science at Université du Québec à Montréal (UQAM). Director of CEIM and LATICCE, she has developed an expertise well recognized in Canada and abroad on digital transformations, Internet governance, transnational economic and trade issues as well as on the more specific issue of the discoverability of digital cultural products.

Jean-Robert Bisailon is Co-director of LATICCE for the music sector. He's a former board member of SOCAN and the Songwriters Association of Canada. He is currently pursuing a PhD diploma at the Department of political science at UQAM on issues related to data governance, metadata and informational self-determination.

Guy-Philippe Wells is director of research on economic and business models at LATICCE. He is actually pursuing a PhD diploma at the Department of political science at UQAM. His research interests focus on the political economy of international relations, regionalism and economic integration, particularly the effects of globalization and the Internet on culture.

Introduction

In a world transformed by the Internet, cloud computing, AI and big data, the world community is increasingly looking for ways to regulate digital giants such as Apple, Amazon, Google, Facebook and Microsoft. In the cultural and media industry, these digital giants along with Spotify and Netflix, have disrupted traditional value chains and actors.

Unregulated compared to nationally embedded cultural industries, they have a great competitive advantage. Increasingly, those data rich enterprises are the subject of scrutiny by public authorities that are struggling to adapt their policies and regulatory frameworks. From their capacity to escape fiscal systems to projects of Google Brain and total data collections, there is nobody that can escape their reach and their potential control and manipulation. In a nutshell, having left autoregulation do the work since the emergence of rapid technological changes in the 1990s, national policies and regulatory frameworks are now lagging far behind

and the repercussions are numerous. If digital transformations bring opportunities that have been recognized (Rioux and al, 2015...), there are also market failures and shortcomings to autoregulation, especially when public interest is concerned (Thank you for being late, 2016).

The CRTC and the Government of Canada recognize the gap between the regulatory failures and the technological tools that enable fast and efficient systems to emerge. The Yale Report also called for a renewal of the CRTC to be able to act and regulate in a world of fast technological changes. This requires digital tools, data, research and analysis, as well as pragmatic and efficient tools and powers to enforce regulation in the public interest.

The CRTC requested our expertise on metadata for the cultural and musical sectors in order to review its monitoring and regarding an eventual modernizing process. Our analysis is grounded upon 3 years of research on cultural content discoverability measurement and 10 years on metadata and unique IDs exploration. Canadian content and language issues have driven a large portion of our work.

This report contains a series of remarks following our critical, yet constructive analysis of a research and proposal submitted by Oproma, an Information Management & Technology expert firm based in Gatineau. It also introduces many key aspects that we think should be taken into account for the creation of an efficient and pragmatic regulatory framework regarding the music industry. While we basically discuss the modernization of the existing monitoring of CANCON on Radio, we also keep in mind the importance of thinking about a modernization process that can be applied to the increasingly dominant digital platforms.

Having analysed the radio monitoring modernization project of the CRTC, we think this is a necessary step. We also think that it can lead to a new system that could be used for the monitoring and tracking of a similar CANCON on digital streaming platforms. The index currently developed by the CTRC and on which we are briefly commenting, shows the need to do so and that measurement is possible. The research work LATICCE comes to the same conclusions. Methodology showing levels of “plays” and “spins” in the digital world could be refined, developed and become a significant part of an innovative regulatory approach in Canada. This modernization process would obviously be useful in other sectors, notably the audiovisual sector.

CRTC’s Broadcast division has wisely retained the services of computer experts to mine content data and metadata and to study systems architecture of several available sources in order to

create a normalized mapping of required metadata fields. This step was the first to take in order to lead us to the creation of modernized databases and monitoring rules.

Among the data sources explored were also radio broadcaster's. The modernization exercise could relief traditional radio from the burden of fulfilling new prerequisite, like for example, the obligation to supply the ISRC for each of their spins, while supporting them on programming by making compliance easier to reach.

Our task consisted in guiding the prospect of creating a national public music database populated with appropriate metadata. We also reflected on the conditions required to make tracking and monitoring work for artists and creators nowadays left without much information and power to get their fair share of streaming revenues, while balancing the public interest in order to maintain the proper level of access to Canadian content in digital environments.

High level goal for CRTC authoritative database is also to validate MAPL and French Canadian Track status as CANCON remains important and is probably more important on the digital platforms. Finally, we will address issues regarding the limitations and potential solutions to validate English, French or Aboriginal language.

On March 20, 2020, we had submitted 14 questions for Oproma regarding CRTC Database v2.0 (Draft Data Model). In this reply, we will discuss answers provided by CRTC or OPROMA. Overall, we are very satisfied with the answers and have looked forward further interaction via web conference on March 30th, 2020. Replies and complementary questions prepared for this meeting, and answers provided that day are included.

These questions can be classified in three sets of questions: 1) general technical questions; 2) questions related to their technical proposal while questioning the CRTC methodological framework; and 3) questions that actually deal with the modernizing of regulatory framework in Canada regarding the use and impact of digital technologies. These three sets of questions are distinct but very much articulated. Here, we addressed them in the two sections that follow: 1) technical questions and 2) methodological and regulatory issues. In the concluding section, we formulate the recommendations to build on the draft model and to reform regulation of cultural industries in Canada which must be based on pragmatic and smart use of new digital technologies.

We anticipate more interactions and perhaps reporting from our part, in September, once a new sample validation is done on some 1000 Canadian titles on digital platforms. We should then be able to dig further into technical methods to automate a streaming content validation process.

Technical questions

Within the existing regulatory framework, the CRTC has made significant efforts in addressing the urgent need to modernize radio surveillance regarding CANCON. We believe that within the framework of the mandate, OPROMA proposed a solid technical analysis that can prove to be very beneficial for Canada and the music industry. The triangulation of seven (7) sources available in Canada and elsewhere, is interesting and an important step forward. We asked why the project is based on building a new database using relational tools which may not be the best way to go further given the open data logic we may later publish some of the fields online. A graph approach could be more pertinent. From the start of the development of the pilot project, the objectives surrounding the open database were established by the CRTC radio monitoring team. The database model is a preliminary draft with the information at hand at the time and there may be missing tables and fields. We think that the CRTC should pursue this issue in the consolidation process. We also highlighted the fact that the Draft Data Model does not offer a Works table. This was actually not in the actual mandate and the determining variable is the CRTC negotiations of sharing agreements. We agree that the CRTC should, by federal laws, request submissions from different organizations to carry out this work and that based on the data analyzed, Oproma should include a Works table. We also believe that the CRTC should make sure that the following questions find an answer in the next few months.

We recommend the building of an automatic *CANCON Radio Track Validator*. Such a solution is undoubtedly a required step to monitor closely and efficiently the trends and evolution of the music industry in Canada. Nevertheless, studies we have undergone show that automating and validating authoritative metadata against the digital codec of a recorded artefact (MP3 or other) will be a complex and challenging issue involving highly sophisticated music information retrieval technologies and robust ties between audio and metadata.

- Could OPROMA work with LATICCE with regards to building an automatic Track Validator, discoverability measurement or Audit process?
- Is OPROMA's solution the best available for long term monitoring and tracking, is it adapted to the needs of the CTRC and cultural public policy issues?

- Has OPROMA normalized and documented business rules to reap and analyse the testing data and can you share it with us?
- Is M.i² Core solution totally proprietary?
- Is the TI solution protected more generally from cyber threats during transfers?
- Can OPROMA certify the security of your communications and servers?
- What could improve this TI solution to build this database, its aggregation?

Methodological and regulatory issues

DATA - ensuring collaboration for a rich database

The Oproma Study was based on the triangulation of CBC-SRC RLMS and Disco as well as MusicBrainz considered the most complete databases available and SOCAN as the determining source to validate the CANCON value based on work share. We understand that the current proposal is based on actual shared data and limitations in its scope as well as on available sources.

For LATICCE, one of the most important problems is the absence of references to the IPN (International Performer Number) in the project. Of course, the CRTC does not regulate the music industry, but the broadcast industry, and rights companies like the SOCAN, the producers or the Labels, essentially provide the data they want to share. This situation is no longer acceptable since data protection and data sharing is so vital for the future of the cultural industries. From the LATICCE point of view, the IPN (recording performers ID) should be coupled with the ISRC (recordings ID), and in turn with the ISWC (underlying work ID) and the IPI (musical works creators ID). **We see a 4 MUST identifiers combination to ensure digital music tracking.** Furthermore, the ISNI (persons and organisations ID) and perhaps the MBID (MusicBrainz ID) should be used as check values.

The IPI is private and only available to members of copyright collectives. SOCAN is the only Canadian source for this information. Access to IPI and ISWC is open to the public but limited to manual searching and no means of exporting. SOCAN's disclosure of the ISWC and IPI is subject to limitations by CISAC, the international confederation of copyright collectives. On the other end, CISAC is in the midst of developing the ISWC Service, a more open service for bulk

retrieval. These contextual elements should be further discussed with SOCAN to find out when a fully transparent collaboration could be reached.

The MetaMusic framework and mandate (supported by Canada Council) significantly overlaps the CRTC Digital Radio Monitoring project. In this regard, we believe Canadian Heritage should make sure no waste of public support occurs as both projects plan on publishing a public segment of a musical works database. We underline the fact that, while the CRTC relies on the collaboration of several copyright collectives to reach its goals, most of these organisations are already members of the governance body put together by MetaMusic :

<https://metamusique.ca/ressources>. We also underline the fact that, with regards to French Canadian content, further insight may also be found in the MetaMusic project :

<https://metamusic.ca/>.

We recommend considering offering the public segment of the CRTC database using Linked Open Data norms and wish to point to your attention the innovation achieved by the performing arts sector on the matter, notably CAPACOA's Linked Digital Future initiative¹.

Data is important but the world of data can be incomplete, false or biased. This is why it is so important that the best identification of cultural products is achieved and that the metadata is more complete and adequate for reaching regulatory objectives. Access to data and the openness of data should be core principles of this project. It is our experience in our research on discoverability that all partners are well intended but that it is always difficult to structure (due to complexity and costs) or to share data. Consumer Use Data is strategic, and most initiatives to build a far reaching and global normalisation of data has partly failed so far (wide adoption of DDEX in Canada for exemple). In this context, **the regulatory framework should ensure the participation of all in the construction of rich, shared and publicly administered data trust** with transparency principle at its core. The CRTC must ensure that information is shared and made public through regulator means. Artists, creators and other rights holders should be involved at some point in validating this process of identification for transparency.

We understand that paid solutions were not considered in the pilot project. CBC-SRC, LAC, SOCAN, Bell Media, Rogers and others never received payments for data shared. OPROMA and LATICCE agree on the significance of MusicBrainz and **we therefore recommend that the CRTC look into different scenarii to engage with MusicBrainz to find grounds for a collaboration** (i. e. : test of the live data feed that could allow for an exploration of

¹ Saumier-Finch, « Interlinking Datasets to Build Better Listings – LDFI ». <https://linkeddigitalfuture.ca/2020/04/03/interlinking-datasets-to-build-better-listings/>

collaborative efforts to develop the new tracking and monitoring system or becoming a Metabrainz foundation Unicorn Tier supporter). All agree that benefits could be very significant.

Recommendations

Identification is key and there is an urgent need to improve the standards and practices involving normalized and shared standards for the ID of musical tracks, artists, creators, rights holders, country of origin :

- a. IPN, IPI, ISWC, ISRC is the match that will be the game changer;
- b. The triangulation method is a good practice but new data could allow for much more;
- c. CRTC needs access to more data to regulate, notably geolocation of the recording process (perhaps via UN-LOCODE and GeoNames) or identification of the producers of the digital goods and artefacts (perhaps via the ISNI).

We recommend:

1. That CRTC proceeds with the pilot project based on the triangulation;
2. That the 4 MUST (IPN/IPI/ISWC/ISRC) is integrated at the core of the method;
3. That the CRTC is empowered to oblige industry actors to provide the necessary data;
4. That the CRTC is empowered to oblige industry actors to capture essential data at the source : Musical creators and publishers, recording producers and performers should be provided with the tools to do it now and for the future, and also to cover the costs of historical update of the commercial documentation for Canadian goods in order to reach the professional standards of other countries and world market.

Adapting MAPL (Section in French)

L'idée d'utiliser les fonds publics pour financer le développement de la culture canadienne n'est pas récente. En 1951, le rapport Massey¹ prônait le financement par le gouvernement fédéral d'un large éventail d'activités culturelles, pour, notamment, contrer une « dépendance permanente et dangereuse à la culture américaine » (Stewart 2006). Dans la foulée du rapport Massey sera créé le Conseil des arts du Canada (1957) et par la suite, le gouvernement Trudeau créera le Conseil de la radiodiffusion et des télécommunications canadiennes (1968) qui sera responsable de la mise en œuvre des politiques de contenus canadiens. Une part importante de la justification au financement gouvernemental et à la réglementation du secteur culturel réside dans l'importance accordée à la distinction entre les cultures canadiennes et américaines.

« The Canadian broadcasting system is the result of the interaction of popular social pressure for public service broadcasting, pressure from financial interests to keep broadcasting in the commercial sector and provide a favourable condition in which to do broadcasting business, and the political project of maintaining 'Canada' as an entity distinct from the United States of America and united against the periodic threat of disintegration posed by Quebec. » (Raboy, 1990:xii)

Les quotas de diffusion de productions canadiennes à la radio sont devenus réalités au début des années 1970. La culture étant de juridiction provinciale à plusieurs égards, la responsabilité fédérale en matière de radiodiffusion et de télécommunications offrait un terrain fertile pour l'établissement de réglementations fédérales. La Loi sur la radiodiffusion de 1968 met la table en créant le CRTC et en établissant que :

« les entreprises de radiodiffusion au Canada font usage de fréquences qui sont du domaine public et que de telles entreprises constituent un système unique, ci-après appelé le système de la radiodiffusion canadienne, comprenant des secteurs public et privé ; que le système de la radiodiffusion canadienne devrait être possédé et contrôlé effectivement par des Canadiens de façon à sauvegarder, enrichir et raffermir la structure culturelle, politique, sociale et économique du Canada ; (Loi sur la radiodiffusion, S.R.C. 1970, chap. B-11) »

Le 12 février 1970, le CRTC propose d'introduire un niveau minimal de diffusion de contenu canadien de 30 % sur les radios AM. Ce niveau était largement inférieur à celui de 60 % exigé des

diffuseurs télévisuels. L'exigence de diffusion de contenu canadien de 30 % sera élargie à la diffusion FM entre 1975 et 1991 et passera à 35 %. Les stations de radio francophone doivent de plus consacrer 65 % de la musique populaire qu'ils diffusent à des sélections francophones. C'est ainsi en 1970 que furent établis les critères définissant ce qui constitue un contenu canadien.

Pour être considérée comme contenu canadien, une pièce musicale doit généralement remplir au moins deux des conditions suivantes :

- M (musique) — la musique doit être composée entièrement par un Canadien.
- A (artiste interprète) — la musique ou les paroles sont interprétées principalement par un Canadien.
- P (production) — la pièce musicale est une prestation en direct qui est :
 - soit enregistrée en entier au Canada,
 - soit interprétée en entier au Canada et diffusée en direct au Canada.
- L (paroles lyriques) — les paroles sont écrites entièrement par un Canadien.

Il existe quatre cas particuliers où une pièce musicale peut être considérée comme contenu canadien.

- La pièce musicale a été enregistrée avant janvier 1972 et remplit l'une des conditions ci-dessus.
- Il s'agit d'une interprétation instrumentale d'une œuvre musicale écrite ou composée par un Canadien.
- Il s'agit d'une interprétation d'une œuvre musicale qu'un Canadien a composée exclusivement pour des instruments.
- La pièce musicale a été interprétée en direct ou enregistrée après le 1er septembre 1991, elle satisfait au critère relatif à l'interprète ou à la production, et un Canadien ayant collaboré avec un non-Canadien se voit attribuer au moins la moitié des droits pour les paroles et la musique – ainsi qu'en attestent les dossiers d'une société reconnue de perception des droits d'auteur, telle que la Société canadienne des auteurs, compositeurs et éditeurs de musique (SOCAN, Canada), Broadcast Music Incorporated

(BMI), l'American Society of Composers, Authors and Publishers (ASCAP) et la SESAC (États-Unis).

Aux fins d'application du système MAPL, un 'Canadien' s'entend au sens des définitions données dans le Règlement sur la radio du CRTC, à savoir :

- un citoyen canadien ;
- un résident permanent au sens de la Loi sur l'immigration de 1976 ;
- une personne dont le lieu ordinaire de résidence était situé au Canada durant les six mois qui ont précédé son apport à une œuvre musicale, à un spectacle ou à un concert ;
- un titulaire, c.-à-d. une personne autorisée à exploiter une station de radio.

Le débat entourant les obligations de diffusion de contenu canadien a précédé la réglementation mise en œuvre par le CRTC en 1970. Il a d'abord reposé sur le fait que les Canadiens souhaitaient écouter des chansons plus modernes que les chansons traditionnelles canadiennes, présentant une vision étriquée de la production canadienne. (Richardson, 2008). Radio-Canada et Alliance of Canadian Cinema, Television and Radio Artists (ACTRA) furent parmi les premiers promoteurs des quotas de diffusion alors que les propriétaires de station radio s'y opposèrent. Dans les mots de Pierre Juneau, premier président du CRTC, la réglementation sur le contenu canadien est un moyen d'assurer la diversité et de rendre disponible du contenu qui serait autrement censuré par les distributeurs et les diffuseurs qui ne sont intéressés que par le contenu qui a déjà fait ses preuves sur les marchés étrangers. (Edwarson, 2008 : 380)

La justification du pouvoir réglementaire du CRTC repose sur la nature publique des ondes radio et sur la limite physique du nombre de fréquences disponibles. L'octroi d'une licence constitue ainsi un privilège accordé à un diffuseur lui permettant d'exploiter un bien public pour générer des profits privés.

« En échange du privilège d'avoir accès aux ondes et aux fréquences publiques du Canada et comme condition d'obtention d'une licence, les diffuseurs privés doivent atteindre les objectifs politiques, sociaux, économiques et culturels prévus dans la loi et qui visent à appuyer, à renforcer et à valoriser les objectifs susmentionnés. L'application de quotas sur la diffusion de contenu musical local fait partie de leur engagement. »
(Shelley, 2012)

Un élément de controverse à travers les années est le traitement réservé aux grands succès par les stations de langues anglaises. Aux débuts de l'application des quotas, les radios ont concentré la diffusion d'œuvres canadiennes sur celles de quelques artistes déjà très populaires, ce qui, pour plusieurs, contrevenait à l'objectif de favoriser une plus grande diversité sur les ondes canadiennes. Le CRTC a établi en 1975 une réglementation prévoyant que le niveau de grands succès diffusé par les radios commerciales FM anglophones devait être inférieur à 50 % de la musique diffusée chaque semaine. En 2009, le CRTC a décidé d'abolir cette restriction, à l'exception des régions de Montréal et de Gatineau, où les radios francophones, soumises au quota de 65 % de diffusion francophone, sont en concurrence avec des radios anglophones qui ne le sont pas. L'analyse du CRTC est à l'effet que :

« le principal objectif de la politique sur la diffusion de grands succès dans les marchés de langue anglaise est de protéger les stations de radio AM de musique rétro. Dans l'ensemble, les résultats financiers démontrent que cette politique n'a pas eu l'effet escompté et que les stations de musique rétro se heurtent à une concurrence grandissante de la part des stations FM et d'autres sources comme la radio par satellite et par Internet qui diffusent un nombre considérable de 'disques d'or'. » (CRTC 2009)

Les tensions demeurent entre les diffuseurs radio et les artistes quant à la nécessité des quotas, particulièrement pour ce qui est du contenu francophone. En 2015, deux diffuseurs majeurs au Québec (Bell et Cogeco) se sont groupés pour réclamer du CRTC une diminution de ces quotas de 65 % à 35 %. Ils font état d'un éloignement entre la consommation réelle de musique francophone au Québec et le niveau des quotas, créant une perte de pertinence des diffuseurs radio francophones. À notre avis, les défis posés à la réglementation MAPL sont de deux ordres : économiques et fonctionnels.

Le débat sur les incidences économiques de la réglementation a exposé que les stations radio sont demeurées très rentables pour la plupart à travers le temps. Il sera difficile de prétendre que la réglementation encadrant leurs activités nuit gravement à la compétitivité des radios alors que les marges bénéficiaires demeurent élevées. En ce sens, une part du MAPL est lié à l'avenir de la rentabilité économique des stations de radio.

Les revenus des stations radio sont restés stable depuis 2010, malgré le choc de la transformation numérique. Le niveau de bénéfices a même augmenté au cours des 20 dernières années. La transformation numérique, qui a eu des effets dévastateurs sur plusieurs industries, n'a pas encore durement frappé le modèle d'affaires de la radio.

Marges bénéficiaires de la radio commerciale au Québec

Source : Centre d'études sur les médias, mars 2019. En ligne :

<https://www.cem.ulaval.ca/economie/donnees-financieres/radio/>

Les plateformes numériques d'écoute en ligne (PNEL) n'ont pas encore réussi à investir le territoire du modèle d'affaire de la radio qui repose sur la vente de publicité (97% des revenus des radios commerciales) souvent locale et ciblée, la gratuité pour les usagers, autant pour l'accès au contenu qu'à celui de la transmission, le contenu original et local et la relation intime établie entre les auditeurs et les animateurs. Les PNEL ont évidemment identifié les revenus publicitaires des radios comme source potentielle de leur croissance. Spotify l'exprime clairement :

‘With our Ad-Supported Service, we believe there is a large opportunity to grow Users and gain market share from traditional terrestrial radio. In the United States alone, traditional terrestrial radio is a \$14 billion market, according to BIA/Kelsey. The total global radio advertising market is approximately \$28 billion in revenue, according to Magna Global. With a more robust offering, more on-demand capabilities, and access to personalized playlists, we believe Spotify offers Users a significantly better alternative to linear broadcasting.’ (Spotify, 2018: 2)

Figure 3-6 Audio revenues (2013–2018)

Jusqu'à maintenant, les obstacles sont encore trop nombreux pour que les PNEL attaquent directement le modèle d'affaires des radios, mais les développements technologiques et la capacité d'adaptation des PNEL n'excluent pas qu'il le soit dans l'avenir. On peut envisager que les stations radio qui diffusent surtout de la musique soient concurrencées par les PNEL si jamais le coût de la communication cellulaire devait réduire de manière importante, par exemple. Les tensions deviendraient alors beaucoup plus fortes et les radios réclameraient avec plus de vigueur que la réglementation soit relâchée ou que les plateformes y soient soumises.

Il apparaît comme étant probable que ce débat resurgisse au cours des prochaines années. Si le gouvernement canadien souhaite conserver le système MAPL, les avenues pour l'intégrer aux PNEL ne sont pas encore clairement identifiées. Le mode de fonctionnement des PNEL est très différent de celui des radios et la simple application de la réglementation actuelle à celles-ci paraît impraticable. Nous croyons qu'il est nécessaire d'amorcer une réflexion sur les moyens d'adapter la réglementation MAPL au mode de fonctionnement des PNEL. **Nous recommandons que le CRTC crée un groupe de travail pour évaluer les moyens d'exiger un minimum de contenu canadien aux plateformes numériques d'écoute en ligne (PNEL).**

Sur le plan fonctionnel, la réglementation MAPL actuelle limite les possibilités de collaborations internationales par les artistes canadiens souhaitant que leur musique soit reconnue comme étant canadienne. Le développement de moyens technologiques et la croissance des contacts internationaux font en sorte qu'il est possible que les artistes canadiens soient de plus en plus appelés à collaborer avec des artistes étrangers. Les critiques à la réglementation MAPL provenant des artistes canadiens sont sans doute celles qui risquent le plus de la déstabiliser, tout en étant ceux pour lesquels la réglementation existe. Il nous semble nécessaire d'ajuster la réglementation MAPL.

Considering the many controversies over MAPL over the years, its modernization is probably required to improve the identification of CANCON. We recommend requesting “place of recording” information from SOCAN, Re:Sound, CMRRA, AVLA, SOPROQ, Artisti and any other organizations involved in the monetization of the sound recording artefact. It is important to identify any information and data that could facilitate the modernization process, especially when considering the willingness for the CRTC to extend monitoring to digital platforms. **We recommend that the CRTC carry out this modernizing of the methodology used for CANCON in order to better reflect the canadian content along the value chain in the traditional and digital sectors.** This is especially important because of the discoverability barriers that we have documented at LATICCE.

We agree that any additional metadata can and should be added if deemed pertinent and that the CRTC should keep an ongoing process of adjusting these fields in this fast evolving music industry to make sure its modernization process remains adapted to data challenges in the future.

Recommendations with regards to MAPL

MAPL must be revisited, improved, be more transparent and agile in times of technological changes.

- We recommend rethinking the “place of recording” requirement and if maintained, to frame the information needed from SOCAN, Re:Sound, CMRRA, AVLA, SOPROQ, Artisti. This requirement is voiced differently at MetaMusic where the sound recording producer is considered the needed element more than the actual geolocation of the sessions.

- The calculation of shares needed to establish the product origin should be reviewed.
- The CRTC should keep an ongoing process of adjusting these fields in this fast evolving music industry.
- The CRTC must explore a professional CISAC ISWC Service access to retrieve aggregated, de-identified and geolocated M and L splits (aside from using the Web ISWC Search approach), or to make sure that the MetaMusic project component organisations contribute fully to its future framework and allow the retrieval of this information.

Future perspectives on the draft model

Obviously this project responds to a real problem regarding the status of radio monitoring in Canada. Regulation must be in tune with fast changing technology and its impact on the music industry. The Draft Model can provide for better monitoring and tracking in the music sector. The new streaming actors have benefitted from an institutional and regulatory gap that can no longer be tolerated since powerful traditional actors are (back and) now fully in control of the industry.

Ultimately, any successful model will need to require artists, producers and distributors to collaborate in building a transparent, fair and efficient system of monitoring and regulating the music industry. **We recommend that research be conducted on the situations in Europe and in the US concerning the issue of monitoring radio and digital platforms (notably the MLC in the USA, its impacts, benefits, limits and relevancy for Canada).** In this section, we will introduce some interesting aspects of the Music Modernization Act. **We also recommend that the CRTC engage in research in relation to the discoverability of cultural products.**

Music Modernization Act (Section in French)

Le Music Modernization Act (MMA) (H.R. 1551, Pub. L. 115–264) a été adopté le 11 octobre 2018 afin de mettre à jour la législation à la suite des changements technologiques dans l'industrie de la musique. La loi est organisée en trois parties :

- Music Licensing Modernization Act : Il remplace la structure existante de licences obligatoires chanson par chanson pour la production et la distribution d'œuvres musicales par un système de licences générales pour les fournisseurs de musique numérique afin d'effectuer et de distribuer des livraisons de phonogrammes numériques (par exemple, téléchargements permanents, téléchargements limités ou flux interactifs).
- Classics Protection and Access Act: Il intègre partiellement les enregistrements sonores d'avant 1972 au système fédéral de droit d'auteur. La législation a créé un nouveau chapitre 14 de la loi sur le droit d'auteur, intitulé 17 United States Code, qui, entre autres, étend les recours en cas de violation du droit d'auteur aux propriétaires d'enregistrements sonores fixés avant le 15 février 1972 (« Enregistrements sonores avant 1972 ») lorsque les enregistrements sont utilisés sans autorisation. Le nouveau chapitre comprend plusieurs limitations et exceptions à l'admissibilité à ces recours et procédures administratives connexes, qui sont traitées ci-dessous.
- Allocation for Music Producers Act: Il permet aux producteurs de musique, aux mixeurs ou aux ingénieurs du son de recevoir des redevances perçues pour l'utilisation d'enregistrements sonores en vertu de la licence statutaire en vertu de l'article 114 en codifiant un processus dans lequel le collectif désigné (Sound Exchange) distribuera ces redevances à ces parties sous une « lettre de directive.²

Le 8 juillet 2019, le U.S. Copyright Office a nommé le Mechanical Licensing Collective (MLC) afin, qu'à compter de janvier 2021, il émette et administre des licences mécaniques générales aux services de streaming et de téléchargement éligibles (fournisseurs de services numériques ou DSP) aux États-Unis. Le MLC percevra ensuite les redevances dues au titre de ces licences auprès des DSP et rémunérera les auteurs-compositeurs, compositeurs, paroliers et éditeurs de musique. Le MLC construit une base de données des œuvres musicales accessible au public, ainsi qu'un portail que les créateurs et les éditeurs de musique peuvent utiliser pour soumettre et maintenir leurs données sur les œuvres musicales. Ces outils visent à garantir que les créateurs et les éditeurs de musique sont correctement payés.³

² Copyright.gov. 2019. The Music Modernization Act. En ligne: <https://www.copyright.gov/music-modernization/>

³ MLC. 2020. About us. En ligne: <https://www.themlc.com/our-story>

Source: MLC.2020. How it works. En ligne: <https://www.themlc.com/how-it-works>

Le MLC recevra 33,5 millions de dollars pour les frais de démarrage et une évaluation annuelle initiale pour 2021 de 28,5 millions de dollars. Tous les coûts seront répartis entre les titulaires de licence, les services les plus importants payant une part plus importante.⁴

This Modernization Act will have great impacts in the United States. It will also have impacts on Canada. **The CRTC should conduct research on the nature of these impacts and compare its modernization process and its data project with the MLC Database that seems to be innovative.**

⁴ MLC. 2020. The Mechanical Licensing Collective, Digital Licensee Coordinator Announce Landmark Agreement. 14 décembre 2019. En ligne: <https://www.themlc.com/press/mechanical-licensing-collective-digital-licensee-coordinator-announce-landmark-agreement>

Toward discoverability targets and algorithm audits

The modernization process can potentially resolve many of the problems and obstacles that LATICCE has encountered in the last 4 years (metadata interoperability or standards, access to a well defined concept or list of Canadian or FR content, a well designed IT solution linked to all pertinent data). This could allow a huge step for research and monitoring of the presence, visibility and recommendation of CANCON that is central to digital cultural policy (in the making). **We recommend that the database be constructed in ways to ensure the monitoring of cultural industries regarding discoverability objectives** (presence, visibility, recommendation) and data governance (audio & metadata authoritative matching, privacy, transparency, AI audit and governance via some Data Trust mechanism).

Data and algorithms are key aspects of the future of the economy worldwide. Yet, its structure and validation are left mostly to autoregulation. How can we certify data and algorithms in a way that corresponds to good business practices, sound economic and legal principles to protect individual and collective rights? How can we identify and comprehend these rights and determine good regulation in a time of fast changing and disruptive technologies? On what principles do we conceive state intervention and regulation and how can we justify and make them acceptable to all stakeholders and going concerns? These questions are important to structure the future. The CRTC must open this black box and find ways to regulate how algorithms work and impact on the treatment of CANCON.

Canada is engaged in a consultation process on the appropriate regulation of artificial intelligence (The Office of the Privacy Commissioner of Canada Consultation: Proposals for ensuring appropriate regulation of artificial intelligence,

<https://www.priv.gc.ca/en/about-the-opc/what-we-do/consultations/consultation-ai/>)

The proposals are mostly aimed at privacy and transparency issues but the impact of AI can also be explored for distinct groups and communities. Based on our research, we can reasonably state that AI has a significant role in defining what people are listening or reading. Proposal 9 of the OPC is about requiring “organizations to ensure data and algorithmic traceability, including in relation to datasets, processes and decisions made during the AI system lifecycle”. Algorithmic traceability would facilitate the application of several principles, including accountability, accuracy, transparency, data minimization as well as access and correction. International organizations and many states are taking steps in this regulatory effort.

- The OECD *Principles on Artificial Intelligence*.
- Singapore A *Proposed Model Artificial Intelligence Governance Framework*.
- France’s data protection authority (Commission nationale de l’informatique et des libertés—CNIL), has recommended the development of a “national platform” for algorithmic auditing.
- The *Algorithmic Accountability Act* (AAA), which would give the US Federal Trade Commission (FTC) new powers to require companies to assess their machine learning systems for bias and discrimination.

We live in the age of the algorithm and this should lead to fairness. But are algorithms neutral and fair? Cathy O’Neil, in *Weapon of Math destruction*, revealed that this is not the case. Opacity, autoregulation fuel and reinforce discrimination and O’Neil calls on policy makers to regulate their use. Shoshana Zuboff, in *Surveillance Capitalism*, thinks the same as business models and economic concentration is signaling a mutation of the economic system . Few firms appropriate, control and trade data to impact on people’s behavior and consumption patterns. The GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) in Europe is, according to her, a step in the right direction with transparency rules and having platforms not publish offensive content.

The Yale Report (2020)⁵ has emphasized the need for discoverability obligations on audio and audiovisual content undertakings⁶. The Yale report also stressed the public interest in regulating big data. This is going to be extremely important in the context of future introduction of 5G networks and all the increased connectedness that will link humans, objects and machines. We believe recommandation 92 and 93 are important for Canada, and for its

⁵ Gouvernement du Canada, « Rapport Yale : L’avenir des communications au Canada ».

⁶ Recommendation 63: To ensure that Canadians are able to make informed choices and that Canadian content has sufficient visibility and is easy to find on the services that Canadians use, we recommend that the CRTC impose discoverability obligations on all audio or audiovisual entertainment media content undertakings, as it deems appropriate, including:

- catalogue or exhibition requirements;
- prominence obligations;
- the obligation to offer Canadian media content choices; and
- transparency requirements, notably that companies be transparent with the CRTC regarding how their algorithms operate, including audit requirements.

cultural industries⁷. The data enterprises like Netflix gather must be regulated in the public interest.

In the meantime, it is important to be prudent as regulations could be a trade policy issue.

According to Reuters (March 24, Reuters) - Mexican senators are set to vote : “on a proposal that would force streaming platforms like Netflix Inc and Amazon.com Inc to ensure national content makes up at least 30% of their catalogs, a plan the industry argues would drive up costs and make it harder for small players to compete. The U.S. government has engaged the Mexican government about the issue, a spokesperson for the U.S. embassy said. The proposal, drafted by Senator Ricardo Monreal of President Andres Manuel Lopez Obrador’s MORENA party, could violate the United States-Mexico-Canada Agreement, the newly approved trade deal between the three countries, Mexico’s Internet Association wrote in a letter to senators seen by Reuters.”

⁷ Recommendation 92: We recommend that Statistics Canada, the CRTC, the Competition Bureau, the Office of the Privacy Commissioner and other relevant regulatory authorities be charged by the federal government with examining the use of Big Data by dominant online platform providers and potential threats to privacy, competition, consumer protection, cultural sovereignty, democratic institutions, and taxation, and make recommendations on legislation that may be appropriate to address these matters.

Recommendation 93: We recommend that the Ministers of Canadian Heritage and of Industry direct the CRTC to gather information, audit, and intervene, if necessary, with regard to how services covered by the Broadcasting Act and the Telecommunications Act combine algorithms and artificial intelligence with Big Data, in order to respond quickly to changes in the communications services, improve transparency, and promote trust.

Conclusion

Our very last section will offer a complete list of recommendations LATICCE would find fit to consider or implement in connection with CRTC's Radio Monitoring System / Digital / Transformation & Metadata Normalization project.

We have grounded those recommendations on 4 years of research on cultural content discoverability, many discussions held with industry components, involvement on several sector work groups (both in Canada and the province of Quebec), in depth study of International standards such as DDEX, ISO unique IDs (ISWC, ISRC, ISNI) and testimony at public consultations. We have also been invited to comment and ask questions on Oproma's January 27th 2020 Digital Transformation Metadata Normalization Report.

The current evolution of broadcasting and communications in Canada is calling upon major changes. LATICCE has welcomed the relevance of the Yale Report and its findings and many of our recommendations try to reflect those in the form of potential pragmatic actions.

We hope our contribution will find resonance and we remain available to answer any unclear or additional issue.

Recommendations (complete list)

1. We recommend that the CRTC proceed with the Broadcast INDEX pilot project based on the triangulation method defined in the Oproma Study (page 9);
2. We recommend that the 4 MUST unique IDs - IPN/IPI/ISWC/ISRC - are integrated at the core of the method (page 7);
3. We recommend that the CRTC is empowered to oblige industry copyright and neighbouring right collectives to provide the necessary data (page 9);
4. We recommend that the CRTC is empowered to oblige industry actors to capture essential data at the source : Musical creators and publishers, recording producers and performers should be provided with the tools to do it now and for the future, and also to cover the costs of historical update of the commercial documentation for Canadian goods in order to reach the professional standards of other countries and world market (page 9);
5. We recommend requesting “place of recording” information from SOCAN, Re:Sound, CMRRA, AVLA, SOPROQ, Artisti and any other organizations involved in the monetization of the sound recording artefact (page 16);
6. We recommend that CRTC adds data regarding geolocation of the recording process (perhaps via UN-LOCODE and/or GeoNames) and/or identification of the producers of the digital goods and artefacts (perhaps via the ISNI) in its new database (page 9);
7. We recommend that the CRTC look into different scenarii to engage with non-profit MusicBrainz to find grounds for a collaboration : testing of the real time Live Data Feed that could allow for an exploration of collaborative efforts to develop the tracking and monitoring system and becoming a Metabrainz foundation Unicorn Tier supporter (page 8);
8. We recommend that the CRTC creates a task force to evaluate application of Canadian origin content minimum programming rules to streaming music services (*Nous recommandons que le CRTC crée un groupe de travail pour évaluer les moyens d'exiger un minimum de contenu canadien aux plateformes numérique d'écoute en ligne (PNEL)*) (page 15);

9. We recommend that the CRTC carry out modernizing of the methodology used for CANCON and MAPL in order to better reflect the Canadian origin of content along the value chain in the traditional and digital sectors (page 16);
10. We recommend that CRTC keeps an ongoing process of adjusting norms related to Canadian origin of content in this fast evolving music industry (page 17);
11. We recommend that CRTC explore a professional CISAC ISWC Service access to retrieve aggregated, de-identified and geolocated M and L splits (aside from using the Web ISWC Search approach), or to make sure that the MetaMusic project component organisations contribute fully to its future framework and allow the retrieval of this information (page 17);
12. We recommend that research be conducted on the situation in the US concerning the issue of monitoring radio and digital platforms - notably the MLC, its impacts, benefits, limits and relevancy for Canada (page 17);
13. We recommend that research be conducted on the situation in Europe - notably France's Commission nationale de l'informatique et des libertés—CNIL recommendation with regards to the development of a “national platform” for algorithmic auditing (page 24);
14. We support the idea of building an automatic CANCON Track Validator and recommend it should be based on sophisticated music information retrieval technologies. Such a solution is undoubtedly a required step to monitor closely and efficiently the trends and evolution of the music industry in Canada (page 6);
15. We recommend that CRTC and Canadian Heritage make sure no duplication of efforts occur with the MetaMusic project as both projects plan on publishing a public segment of a musical works/recording database. We also recommend considering offering such public segment using Linked Open Data norms (page 7);
16. We recommend that the CRTC database be constructed in ways to ensure the monitoring of cultural industries regarding discoverability objectives (presence, visibility, recommendation) and data governance (audio & metadata authoritative matching, privacy, transparency, AI audit and governance) via some Data Trust mechanism to be defined (page 20).

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Annex - Q&A DRAFT MODEL

The Oproma Study was based on the triangulation of CBC-SRC RLMS and Disco as well as MusicBrainz considered most complete databases available and SOCAN as the determining source to validate the CANCON value based on work share. We first prepared 14 questions for Oproma and discussed via web conference their answers on March 30th. These can be classified in three sets of questions: 1) general technical questions; 2) questions related to their technical proposal while questioning the CRTC methodological framework; and 3) questions that actually deal with the modernizing of regulatory framework in Canada regarding the use and impact of digital technologies.

Observations and questions on Track and Work semantic distinction

Radio reports to CRTC on track usage. We know that these tracks are performing artists recordings of underlying works which lead in return to composers and lyricists. These last two contributors are elements of the MAPL label of content. For a better understanding of the value chain we need to document in the future, LATICCE believes a better distinction should be made between artists in the sense of performing artists (or lead performers or main artists) and artists in the sense of creators (composers and lyricists).

(Q1) Consequently, since we have not seen references to the IPN (International Performer Number) in your result research, have you been looking for this ID or encountered specific problems accessing it?

OPROMA : Note that the CRTC does not regulate the music industry, but the broadcast industry, so the rights companies like the SOCAN, the producers or the labels as an example will essentially provide the data they want to share. Regarding the IPN (International Performer Number) has not been encountered in any sample data received to date, nor in any open-source databases that we have examined (Ex.: MusicBrainz).

LATICCE : We agree and it is also our experience in our research on discoverability that partners are well intended but that it is always difficult to share data at the end of the day, as this is strategic information. We know that most significant initiatives to build a far reaching and global normalisation of data has failed so far (DDEX for ex) . We understand that your solution is based on actual shared data. This is why one of our recommendations will be to oblige all music service providers to participate in a shared and publicly administered data trust to build a

rich database. We believe that this database would ideally integrate IPN which is very important for traceability. This information must be gathered and used for any monitoring system in the digital age. We recommend the addition of the IPN to the 3 MUST of digital music tracking previously identified by OPROMA and the CRTC (IPI, ISWC, ISRC). To make sure that the modernization process is based on the best data available in order to reach CTRC goal, the CRTC must ensure that this information is shared and made public through regulator means.

MusicBrainz Live Data Feed

As mentioned in the Oproma document, we agree that MusicBrainz is one of the most complete database currently available. This is not always officially recognized by the industry stakeholders who often see it as a competitor rather than a complementary source of documentation.

(Q2) Have we enquired into the costs and benefits of becoming a Metabrainz foundation Unicorn Tier supporter or studied the payload of the daily Live Data Feed ?

OPROMA: Oproma is aware of this tier, however paid solutions were not part of the mandate of this report. These solutions will belong to the CRTC. We must say that all of the current negotiations have been carried out by the CRTC asking the project participants for free engagement and as a good corporate citizen. No amount has been compromised or even allocated to organizations such as CBC-SRC, LAC, SOCAN, Bell Media, Rogers and others.

LATICCE : Because of the understanding shared by OPROMA and LATICCE on the significance of MusicBrainz, we recommend that the CRTC look into different scenario and engage in a discussion with MusicBrainz to find grounds for a collaboration. There are many ways that could be explored to build a collaborative relationship with MusicBrainz, notably a test of the live data feed that could allow for an exploration of collaborative efforts to develop the new tracking and monitoring system. The benefits would be real time access to updates and potential inclusion of Canadian data criteria within the worldwide MusicBrainz database.

MAPL and content origin related issues

MAPL stands for Music (music) / Performer (main performer) / Production (place of recording) / Lyrics (lyrics) and determines if the content originates from Canada when two out of the four criteria are met. SOCAN's database is obviously authoritative with regards to Music and Lyrics. In the case of multiple creators, CRTC Public Notice 1993-5 has been published superseding the

idea that Music or Lyric must have been entirely created by Canadians. This is where Share of Works is key.

(Q3) How do we make sure similar criteria is applied to a group acting as the main performer?

CRTC: In order to ensure that a group as a main performer is considered Canadian, a triangulation process allows the CRTC to statute on whether the A can be granted. The first step in the triangulation consists in finding the ISNI number of the band. Second, the data obtained from CBC/SRC offers a variety of high potential indicators ranging from personal names of band members, artists names, and corporate names which can offer another level of confirmation through individual ISNIs. A 50% threshold of Canadian members must be met within a band to be granted the A.

LATICCE : see below

(Q4) What authoritative source do we have regarding the place of recording?

CRTC: The evolution of digital recording practices and process has created unique challenges with regards to identifying places of recording. The studio as is was traditionally defined, even though some do still exist, is in reality obsolete. Artists can record or create music anywhere, anytime, with nothing more than a laptop. When looking to identify a place of recording, labels constitute the most reliable source of information. In cases where the information is not released, the place of recording can be triangulated from various sources (AllMusic, Discogs, MusicBrainz).

Based on the sample data received (except for CBC), we do not have enough data to say we have an authoritative source for place of recording. We do however have the following information :

- From the English CBC database for recordings, we have “Country of Origin” there are 9042 hits for “Canada” out of 637965 records. It should be noted that this was data is collected manually.
- LAC provided some information related to “Place of publication”, however this is related to Albums while reporting is always bases on Tracks. It should be noted that this data is collected manually from various sources: SOCAN , WIKIPEDIA, ALLMUSIC. This data can only be provided manually, export automation within their current software is not supported.

We would recommend requesting “place of recording” information from SOCAN, CMRRA, and other organizations listed in MetaMusic.

LATICCE on questions 3 and 4 : Considering the many controversies over MAPL over the years, its modernization is required to improve the identification of CANCON. It would be important to identify any information and data that could facilitate the modernization process, especially when considering the willingness for the CRTC to extend monitoring to the digital platforms. We recommend that the CRTC carry out this modernizing of the methodology used from CANCON in order to better reflect the canadian content along the value chain in the traditional and digital sectors. This is especially important because of the discoverability barriers that we have documented at LATICCE. With regards to French Canadian content, further insight may be found in the MetaMusic (Canada Council supported) project : <https://metamusic.ca/> We also underline the fact that artists and creators should be involved at some point in validating this process of identification for transparency. Finally we wish to shed light on the fact that the notion of “place of recording” should be replaced with a criteria based on the notion of “recording producer” (being in that sense different from the notion of “artistic producer”).

Oproma Study Document specifics

Data Sources

(Q5) We would like to know which controlled vocabulary was found or is offered to adopt for the required CANCON metadata fields “Category” and “Role”?

OPROMA : The required CANCON metadata fields are per track and were established by CRTC. The “Category” refers to the CRTC music categories: <https://crtc.gc.ca/eng/archive/2010/2010-819.htm> The “Role” refers to the role of the contributor on the track. Ex.: author, lyricist, performer, etc. This controlled vocabulary in use is the minimum information that is required to track CANCON. Any additional metadata can and should be added if deemed pertinent. The full list of required metadata can be found in the Oproma report.

LATICCE : We agree that any additional metadata can and should be added if deemed pertinent and that the CRTC should keep an ongoing process of adjusting these fields in this fast evolving

music industry to make sure its modernization process remains adapted to data challenges in the future.

Sources Analyzed

(Q6) How was access granted in the case of the ISWC and was it where we also accessed the IPI?

OPROMA : Access to ISWC (<https://iswcnet.cisac.org/logon.do>) is open to the public but limited to manual searching and no means of exporting. The IPI is private and only available to members. In the sample data we received, only SOCAN provided that information. The IPI numbers can also be found via Musicbrainz.

(Q7) Have we had a chance to review *SOCAN for developer* Website, has the verification API returned anything interesting?

OPROMA : The SOCAN for developer website has been reviewed and the API is very limited at this time to: Join SOCAN, Member Verification, Request Status, Acknowledgement, Notifications of Live Performance and Works Registration. There is no API for retrieving or querying for information.

Authoritative Sources

(Q8) Could LAC be used for ISNI extraction and attribution? (like BAnQ is about to do in Quebec) and what would be the interest or gain of doing so....?

OPROMA : The LAC sources have been investigated and due to the manual population of the data and lack of automation, this data cannot be leveraged at this time. much of LAC's digital data and metadata is now under the control of the OCLC (a global library cooperative). This information is accessible, but it is sometimes very expensive to acquire. (E.g.; 0,17 cents CAD per data extraction approx.). The Quebec National Library (BAnQ) has not been investigated by Oproma. We must also mention the fact that we had a budget allowing us to explore 7 different sources, we had to prioritize our choices. Having said that ... At this time, we assume the issues would be present as seen at LAC. CRTC could choose to contact them for additional information.

Share of Works

(Q9) SOCAN could probably validate the MAPL - M and L status without disclosing the granular split key and should be keen to do so rather than giving access to their complete and relatively “dirty” database. Have you explored this solution?

OPROMA : Oproma has not had any direct contact with SOCAN. SOCAN has been reluctant to share any information until recently. As an example, the CRTC negotiated from June 2018 to January 2020 in order to obtain SOCAN's IPI. CRTC would have to pursue this avenue directly.

(Q10) Have you explored a professional CISAC ISWC Service access to retrieve the M and L split keys (aside from using the Web ISWC Search approach)? More in the conclusion.

OPROMA : CRTC would have to explore this service further – Oproma does not have mandate to do so.

(Q11) Is the MAPL taking into account the creator's publisher share when validating the place of birth and split key of M and L? (ex.) If Bryan Adams has shared his copyright 40/60 with an American Publishing company, how does it affect the MAPL status of his recordings?

CRTC : We only consider the composers and authors when determining if the song meets the M (Music) and L (Lyrics) conditions. The creator's publisher share is not taken into account as those conditions only mention Canadian creators and not their publishers.

Furthermore, given that it is difficult to have access to the publishing splits from performing rights organizations (Re:Sound and CMRRA refused to share that information with the CRTC), the CRTC determines whether a song gets 0, 0.5 or 1 point for the Music or the Lyrics based on the number of Canadian contributors for each condition. Proceeding this way gives us an accurate result for the majority of Canadian musical selections. When in doubt or if we need more information, then we can refer to recognized performing rights organizations to have the precise publishing splits for the composers and authors. We must also add that the SRC / CBC database has the category MAiPL (e). The (e) signifying exception which indicates that the distribution rights keys are necessary to identify if the title is Canadian.

LATICCE : We wish to comment on the fact that SOCAN never gave priority to the use of ISNI. Mapping IPI and ISNI has had a political history of tensions among stakeholders. YouTube has more recently adopted ISNI and could be a better source for it. YouTube is also working on

alternative IDs which could be looked into by the CRTC. We believe a conversation is possible with such stakeholders.

Open-Data Sources

(Q12) Have we considered obtaining this missing data via founding members of Re:Sound : SOPROQ, CONNECT, AVLA, Artisti?

CRTC : With regards to the various potential sources listed to obtain the missing data, yes they have been considered, and contacted, with varying results. Amongst them, the SOPROQ has accepted to share their data. Despite the intervention and support of Music Canada, re: sound and connect sent a minimum of data, almost the same as we had from SOCAN and CBC-SRC. Finally, based on the information provided, AVLA and Artisti's data was a duplicate of the data obtained from other sources, which made it redundant for our needs, and was therefore discarded.

OPROMA : We must also mention the fact that we had a budget allowing us to explore 7 different sources, we had to prioritize our choices. Despite the intervention and support of Music Canada, re: sound and connect sent a minimum of data, almost the same as we had from SOCAN and CBC-SRC

LATICCE : We believe the best way to use and access the MusicBrainz database is to commit oneself in participating in the collective effort behind this initiative. The CRTC could consider this avenue. Discogs despite being a great source of rich data doesn't offer as much business intelligence data as MusicBrainz, notably the ISO unique IDs like ISNI, ISRC or ISWC. We believe automatic mapping with Discogs could be difficult.

Missing Sources

(Q12) Have you considered obtaining this missing data via founding members of Re:Sound? (SOPROQ, CONNECT, AVLA, Artisti)

CRTC : With regards to the various potential sources listed to obtain the missing data, yes they have been considered, and contacted, with varying results. Amongst them, the SOPROQ has accepted to share their data. Despite the intervention and support of Music Canada, re: sound and connect sent a minimum of data, almost the same as we had from SOCAN and CBC-SRC. Finally, based on the information provided, AVLA and Artisti's data was a duplicate of the data

obtained from other sources, which made it redundant for our needs, and was therefore discarded.

OPROMA : We must also mention the fact that we had a budget allowing us to explore 7 different sources, we had to prioritize our choices. Despite the intervention and support of Music Canada, re: sound and connect sent a minimum of data, almost the same as we had from SOCAN and CBC-SRC

CRTC Database v2.0 (Draft Data Model)

(Q13) Building a new database using relational tools may not be the best way to go further given the open data logic we may later publish some of the fields online. Has a graph approach been considered?

OPROMA : From the start of the development of the pilot project, the objectives surrounding the open database were clearly established by the CRTC radio monitoring team. Thus 3 fundamental aspects of the regulations were chosen in order to prioritize the design of the pilot project. The objectives regarding open data will include data and metadata to identify whether a title is Canadian, French or of certain categories.

The database model is a preliminary draft with the information at hand at the time. This is by no means complete and we acknowledge that there may be missing tables and fields. Contractually, Oproma spent most of his time analyzing data samples rather than developing a new data model.

A graph approach has not been considered at this time due to limited software tools available.

(Q14) The table architecture offered in the Draft Data Model does not offer a Works table. Why was that choice made?

OPROMA : Oproma's mandate was a feasibility mandate and a proposal for a digital design concept for regulatory purposes. It should be mentioned that the work agenda is at the discretion of the CRTC. We must add that we do not recommend starting the work of architecture before the CRTC is finished negotiating sharing agreements. Note also that the CRTC will no doubt, by federal laws, request submissions from different organizations to carry out this important work ... Based on the data analyzed, Oproma believes that a Works table should be included. Further discussions and planning with CRTC will be required before the database can be finalized.

